

4-(2-Pyridylazo) Resorcinol, A Sensitive Amperometric Reagent for Ultramicro Determination of Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+}

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4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol has been employed successfully as an amperometric reagent for the precise determination of Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} . The reagent's sensitivity is high. 0.1409 mg of Pr^{3+} and 0.1442 mg of Nd^{3+} could be detected successfully in 10 ml solution of each ion with an error of less than $\pm 0.8\%$. The titrations have been performed at $\text{pH } 6.1 \pm 0.02$ and an ionic strength of 0.5 M [KCl]. The molar ratio of metal : PAR complexation is found to be 1 : 2. Titrations are not hampered by the presence of fairly large amounts of K^+ , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ti^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , Cl^- , ClO_4^- , CH_3COO^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions. Experimental and calculated statistical data support the utility of the method.

AMONG the various heterocyclic azo dyes¹ PAN, PAR and TAR have been satisfactorily used for the spectrophotometric²⁻⁴ determination of rare earths. 4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol [abbreviated PAR] has also been used for the determination⁵⁻⁷ of V^{5+} , Ti^{4+} , In^{3+} , Mn^{2+} and various other ions. The spectrophotometric method is not suitable when precipitation occurs, nor it can be used at the close proximity of the wave length of absorption of complex and the ligand. It may predict wrong stoichiometric ratio of metal : ligand. Keeping this in mind an attempt has been made to estimate Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} amperometrically using PAR as a reagent. The present paper deals with the results of amperometric titration of these metal ions with PAR, using d.m.e. as indicator electrode. The method is applicable in presence of various other ions.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR or extrapure quality. Pr^{3+} and Nd^{3+} solutions were prepared and standardized¹¹. Solution of 4-(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of monosodium salt of the reagent (E. Merck) and was standardized potentiometrically⁸ in 1 : 1 v/v dioxane-water by standard Pr^{3+} solution. Ionic strength (0.5 M) was adjusted with potassium chloride solution. Dil. hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions were used to adjust the pH at 6.1 ± 0.02 .

Amperometric titrations were made on a manually operated polarograph with multiflex galvanometer (sens. 8.10×10^{-9} amp/div), using d.m.e. as indicator electrode and S.C.E. as reference electrode. The capillary used for d.m.e. had a m value of 2.3733 mg/sec at a drop time 3.0 sec in air free 1 M potassium chloride solution at 41 cm effective height of mercury column ($m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 2.136 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$). An Elico digital pH meter

(model LI-120) was used for measuring pH of the test solutions.

Voltammograms of 4-(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol : The voltammetric studies were carried out on C.I.C., Baroda (India) pen recording polarograph. 4-(2-Pyridylazo) resorcinol gives a well defined polarographic wave at pH 6.1 (Fig. 1-A). The polarograms of PAR at different concentrations were recorded and it was found that diffusion current was proportional to the concentration of PAR.

Fig. 1. A : Polarogram of 1 mM PAR in 0.5 M KCl at pH 6.1.
B : Polarogram of 2 mM metal (Pr^{3+} or Nd^{3+}) in 0.5 M KCl at pH 6.1.

Procedure of amperometric titrations : For titrations, sets of solutions containing known amount of Pr^{3+} or Nd^{3+} in 0.5 M KCl as supporting electrolyte (in 10 ml volume) were prepared and the pH of the solutions were adjusted at 6.1 ± 0.02 . The metal solution was taken into the

TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC TITRATION OF Pr³⁺ AND Nd³⁺ WITH PAR
Plateau potential = -0.85 V vs S.C.E. ; $\mu = 0.5$; pH = 6.1 $\pm$ 0.02

Sl. No.	Approximate concentration (M)	Amount of Pr ³⁺ Taken (mg)	Amount of Pr ³⁺ Found* (mg)	% Error	Coefficient of variation*	Amount of Nd ³⁺ Taken (mg)	Amount of Nd ³⁺ Found* (mg)	% Error	Coefficient of variation*
1.	1 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.1409	0.1400	-0.63	0.89	0.1442	0.1431	-0.76	0.89
2.	2 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.2818	0.2834	+0.56	0.85	0.2882	0.2868	-0.48	0.86
3.	4 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.5636	0.5608	-0.49	0.66	0.5768	0.5798	+0.52	0.70
4.	6 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	0.8454	0.8404	-0.59	0.64	0.8652	0.8628	-0.27	0.86
5.	8 $\times$ 10 ⁻⁴	1.1272	1.1298	+0.23	0.81	1.1536	1.1584	+0.41	0.86
6.	1 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	1.4091	1.4043	-0.34	0.70	1.4424	1.4494	+0.48	0.41
7.	2 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	2.8182	2.8006	-0.62	0.86	2.8948	2.8764	-0.29	0.47
8.	3 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	4.2273	4.2456	+0.43	0.41	4.3272	4.3886	+0.26	0.70
9.	4 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	5.6964	5.6618	-0.45	0.82	5.7920	5.7920	-0.65	0.64
10.	5 $\times$ 10 ⁻³	7.0455	7.0942	-0.69	0.57	7.2120	7.1815	-0.42	

* The values calculated from replicate set of observations for each concentration.

titration cell. The plateau potential [at which Pr³⁺ and Nd³⁺ do not give any diffusion current (Fig. 1-B)] on the wave of PAR i.e., -0.85 V vs S.C.E. was applied and a standard solution of PAR (pH = 6.1 $\pm$ 0.02) was added drop by drop from a 1 cm³ semi micro burette and the current was noted. On plotting galvanometer readings after necessary volume corrections⁹ against titrant volumes, reversed L shaped curve was obtained (Fig. 2). The end point indicated a metal to PAR ratio of 1 : 2 which is in good agreement with the spectrophotometric results observed by Munshi and Dey⁸. Similar results were observed by using PAR as titrate and Pr³⁺ or Nd³⁺ as titrant under the identical experimental conditions, but an L shaped curve was obtained in this case.

Fig. 2. Amperometric titration curve of Pr³⁺ solution with PAR. Concentration of Pr³⁺ solution taken in cell = 0.001M. Concentration of PAR solution = 0.002mM/ml. V = Volume of Pr³⁺ solution taken in cell i.e. 10 ml. v = Volume of PAR solution added.

Effect of diverse ions : The amperometric titrations of the titled metal ions are not in any way hampered by the presence of fairly large amounts

of foreign ions, viz., alkali and alkaline earth metal ions, NH₄⁺, Tl⁺, Cr⁶⁺, Mo⁶⁺, Cl⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻ etc. However, it is found that small amounts of CO₃²⁻, PO₄³⁻, Cd²⁺, Bi³⁺, Pb²⁺, Sb³⁺, Fe²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ interfere seriously in this titrimetric method.

Results and Discussion

The results of amperometric titrations of the titled metal ions are shown in Table 1. The results indicate that PAR is a sensitive reagent for ultramicro determination of Pr³⁺ and Nd³⁺. The minimum amount (nearly 0.14 mg) of each of the said metal ions can be estimated successfully with a practical error of less than $\pm$ 0.8%. In our earlier communications, we reported that Pr³⁺ and Nd³⁺ could be estimated upto 0.70 mg using cupferron¹⁰, ARS¹¹ and XO¹² as amperometric reagents. The present results clearly show the sensitivity of PAR over these reagents. The low detection limit of PAR is nearly 5 times to that observed with the other three reagents. The repeated experimental observations and finally calculated statistical values like coefficients of variation show the accuracy and precision of the method. It is found that the value of coefficient of variation never exceeded 0.9.

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